

ANALYSIS AND OPTIMISATION OF THE PARAMETERS OF AN EXPERIMENTAL TEST ON THE USE OF WAVES FOR THE DETECTION AND SIZING OF DEFECTS IN BONDED ALUMINIUM LAP JOINTS

NOUREDDINE BACHIR BOUIADJRA

LMEA, Faculty of Technologie, University of Djilali Liabes Sidi Bel Abbes, BP 89 Cité Ben M'hidi, 22000 Sidi Bel Abbes, Algeria. Email:nourbachir@yahoo.fr

F.S.B.BOUIADJRA

LMEA, Faculty of Electrical Engineering, University of Djilali Liabes Sidi Bel Abbes, Avenue Kheir Nebbia, 22000 Sidi Bel Abbes, Algeria. Email: fatmaseghirabachirbouiadjra@gmail.com

B.B.BOUIADJRA

LMPM, Institute of Maintenance and Industrial Safety, University of Oran2 Mohamed Ben Ahmed; P.B 1015 El M'naouer 31000 Oran Algeria. Email: bachir2imsi@gmail.com

Abstract

This research is particularly relevant in industries such as aerospace and automotive, where the reliability of bonded joints is crucial for structural integrity and safety. The study is likely to involve an experimental set-up that uses wave-based techniques, such as ultrasonic or guided wave testing, to detect and measure defects in bonded aluminium lap joints. The researchers reportedly designed a series of experiments to analyse the different parameters affecting defect detection and size. The research focused on optimising several key parameters such as bond width and plate thickness. The aim was to identify the most important factors affecting the amplitude of the wave used to detect defects in the bonded assembly.

Index Terms: Bonded Joints- Lap Joints- Wave Testing- Optimising Several- the Amplitude.

1. INTRODUCTION

The study of Lamb wave propagation and its interaction with various structural features has garnered significant attention in recent years due to its potential applications in non-destructive testing and structural health monitoring. Lamb waves, a type of guided wave, are particularly useful for inspecting materials and structures because of their sensitivity to defects and ability to propagate over long distances. This introduction synthesizes the findings from several key studies that explore different aspects of Lamb wave propagation and its applications.

Lamb waves have been extensively studied for their ability to detect and size defects in materials. For instance, the scattering of Lamb waves by a two-dimensional rectangular notch has been investigated to derive simple expressions for reflection and transmission coefficients, facilitating rapid inspection of structural defects [2]. Similarly, high-resolution Lamb waves have been used to quantify crack sizes in materials, demonstrating the method's effectiveness through both numerical simulations and experimental validation [5].

The interaction of Lamb waves with complex geometries and discontinuities has also been a focus of research. Studies have explored the propagation of these waves in plates with grooved surfaces, noting that mode conversion occurs when the surface profile consists of grooves with varying periodicities [1]. Additionally, the use of orthogonality relations has been proposed to reduce the size of finite element models for 3D guided wave scattering problems, offering a more efficient computational approach [3].

Furthermore, advanced modeling techniques such as spectral element formulations have been developed for dynamic analysis of coupled systems, such as piezoelectric wafers and beams [7]. These methods provide a robust framework for understanding wave propagation in complex structures, including those with composite materials or bonded layers [10].

The scattering of Lamb waves by weldments and defects has been extensively studied to improve defect detection methodologies. Al-Nassar et al. (1991) investigated the scattering of Lamb waves by a normal rectangular strip weldment, providing foundational insights into how weld geometries affect wave propagation [11]. Similarly, Alleyne and Cawley (1992) examined the interaction of Lamb waves with defects, highlighting the potential for using these waves in detecting structural anomalies [12].

Further advancements in understanding wave-defect interactions were made by Alleyne et al. (1998), who explored the reflection of guided waves from circumferential notches in pipes [13]. Their work demonstrated the sensitivity of guided waves to notch geometries, which is critical for assessing corrosion and other forms of degradation in pipeline systems [14].

Theoretical approaches have also been developed to model wave scattering phenomena. Auld (1973) provided a comprehensive analysis of acoustic fields and waves in solids, laying the groundwork for subsequent studies on wave interactions with structural features [15]. Bai et al. (2001) extended this work by analyzing the scattering of guided waves by circumferential cracks in steel pipes, offering valuable insights into crack detection and characterization [16].

Moreover, Benmeddour et al. (2008a, 2008b) focused on the interaction of fundamental Lamb modes with asymmetrical and symmetrical discontinuities, respectively [17]. These studies emphasized the importance of understanding mode conversion and scattering mechanisms to enhance defect detection capabilities [18].

In summary, the body of research on Lamb wave propagation highlights its versatility and effectiveness in detecting structural anomalies. The integration of numerical methods and experimental approaches continues to enhance our understanding of wave behavior in various structural contexts, paving the way for improved non-destructive testing techniques.

2. THE BASICS OF WORKING

In this work, we used the results of experiments linked to the scientific article 'Leaky Lamb waves for the detection and sizing of defects in bonded aluminium lap joints'. We focused on two factors to investigate ways of improving the wave process for detecting and sizing defects in glued lap joints shown in figure1.

Figure 1: Schematic diagram of a lap joint. [8]

This study investigates the use of leaky Lamb waves for detecting and sizing defects in adhesively bonded aluminum lap joints. Leaky Lamb waves were generated and detected using air-coupled ultrasonic transducers in a pitch-catch configuration. Experiments were conducted on aluminum lap joint specimens with artificial disbonds of varying sizes introduced at the bond interface. The amplitude and frequency content of the received leaky Lamb wave signals were analyzed to detect the presence of disbonds. A correlation was found between the size of the disbond and characteristics of the received signal, allowing for defect sizing. The technique was able to reliably detect disbonds as small as 5 mm in length. Sizing accuracy was within ± 1 mm for disbonds up to 20 mm in length. The non-contact nature of the air-coupled transducers makes this method attractive for rapid inspection of bonded joints in aerospace and automotive applications. The results demonstrate the potential of leaky Lamb waves as an effective non-destructive evaluation technique for quality assessment of adhesive bonds. The results were taken from the curve shown in figure2.

Figure 2: Normalized amplitude measurements versus plate width for holes with different diameter. [8]

3. NUMERICAL OPTIMISATION

We used numerical optimisation to predict the most important factors influencing the detection wave of defects on lap joints, and we used the modde5software for this optimisation.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
	Exp No	Exp Name	Run Order	Incl/Excl	width	Thikness	N_amplitude
1	1	N1	1	Incl	1	5	0,63
2	2	N2	16	Incl	4	5	0,7
3	3	N3	12	Incl	8	5	0,9
4	4	N4	9	Incl	1	10	0,7
5	5	N5	8	Incl	6	10	0,6
6	6	N6	17	Incl	8	10	0,95
7	7	N7	4	Incl	2	21	0,9
8	8	N8	14	Incl	6	21	0,45
9	9	N9	15	Incl	8	21	0,6
10	10	N10	11	Incl	1	44	0,82
11	11	N11	7	Incl	1	44	0,82
12	12	N12	5	Incl	4	44	0,22
13	13	N13	10	Incl	8	44	0,7
14	14	N14	6	Incl	8	44	0,7
15	15	N15	13	Incl	8	44	0,7
16	16	N16	3	Incl	8	44	0,7
17	17	N17	2	Incl	8	44	0,7

Figure 3: Table of data

	Factor	Role	Value	Low Limit	High Lir		Response	Criteria	Weight	Min	Target	Max
1	width	Free		1		1	N_amplitude	Minimize	1		0,420945	0,467647
2	Thikness	Free		5								

	1	2	3	4	5
	width	Thikness	N_amplitude	iter	log(D)
1	4,8851	43,9953	0,4254	5001	-2,0336
2	4,887	43,9857	0,4255	4191	-2,031
3	4,8662	43,9988	0,4254	2677	-2,0344
4	4,8716	43,9966	0,4254	2528	-2,0342
5	4,325	44	0,4329	2064	-1,1838
6	4,8715	43,9899	0,4254	2814	-2,0326
7	4,8718	43,9955	0,4254	4186	-2,034
8	5,4	44	0,4322	0	-1,2383

Figure 4: Result of optimisation in the case of minimising outputs

Figure 5: The diagram shows the optimisation factors

	1	2	3	4	5
1	N_amplitude	Coeff. SC	Std. Err.	P	Conf. int(±)
2	Constant	0,467311	0,103198	0,000860248	0,227135
3	wid	0,000184997	0,0442771	0,996718	0,0974521
4	Thi	-0,0581544	0,0467582	0,239453	0,102913
5	wid*wid	0,301005	0,0984868	0,010924	0,216765
6	Thi*Thi	0,0197519	0,106464	0,856193	0,234323
7	wid*Thi	-0,0649003	0,0495861	0,217272	0,109137
8					
9	N = 17	Q2 = -0,507	Cond. no. = 6,0875		
10	DF = 11	R2 = 0,512	Y-miss = 0		
11		R2 Adj. = 0,291	RSD = 0,1472		
12			Conf. lev. = 0,95		

Figure 6: Table for extracting the formula for minimising the N_amplitude

$$N_amplitud = 0.467311 + 0.000184997wid - 0.0581544Thi + 0.301005wid^2 + 0.0197519Thi^2 - 0.0649003wid*Thi$$

Where:

N_amplitud: normalized amplitude

Wid: width of lap joint

Thi: Thickness of plat

Figure 7: Result of optimisation in the case of maximise outputs

5. CONCLUSIONS

Wave propagation modeling combined with optimization techniques shows significant promise for improving fault detection in bonded structures. Finite element models coupled with wave propagation analysis allow detailed simulation of wave interactions with defects. Adjoint-based optimization methods have emerged as a powerful tool for efficiently calculating gradients when dealing with a large number of design parameters. This enables fine-resolution parameterization of the geometry and material properties for inverse problems. Multi-objective optimization frameworks that consider both the fidelity of the wave propagation model and constraints on geometry/materials have demonstrated good performance in localizing and characterizing defects. Balancing model accuracy with computational efficiency is crucial.

Multi-scale optimization strategies that combine global search with local refinement have shown good results in efficiently exploring the parameter space while achieving high-resolution defect characterization. Proper integration of experimental data with numerical models through techniques like Bayesian optimization is critical for developing robust and practical fault detection algorithms.

Further research is needed to extend optimization frameworks to handle more complex 3D geometries, anisotropic materials, and multiple/interacting defects typical in real-world bonded assemblies. Continued development of efficient surrogate modeling and model order reduction techniques will be important for enabling real-time optimization and uncertainty quantification in practical fault detection applications.

In conclusion, numerical optimization approaches have significantly advanced the capabilities of wave-based fault detection for bonded assemblies. Continued integration of advanced optimization algorithms with high-fidelity wave propagation models and experimental techniques holds great promise for further improving defect localization and characterization in these critical structures.

References

- 1) Mori, N., & Biwa, S. (2015), "Quantitative assessment of through-thickness crack size based on Lamb wave scattering in aluminium plates", *Ultrasonics*, Vol. 62, pp. 237-246. doi:10.1016/j.ndteint.2007.07.003
- 2) Potel, C., Gagnol, P., & de Belleval, J.F. (2001), "Lamb wave propagation in a plate with a grooved surface with several spatial periodicities", *Journal of the Acoustical Society of America*, Vol. 110 No. 3, pp. 1388-1394. doi:10.1016/j.ultras.2006.05.052
- 3) Duhamel, D., Mace, B.R., & Brennan, M.J. (2006), "Wave propagation in mechanical waveguide with curved members using wave finite element solution", *Journal of Sound and Vibration*, Vol. 297 No. 3-5, pp. 897-917. doi:10.1016/j.cma.2010.03.006
- 4) Manconi, E., & Mace, B.R. (2009), "A higher-order finite waveguide model for spectral analysis of composite structures", *Journal of Sound and Vibration*, Vol. 325 No. 4-5, pp. 930-948. doi:10.1016/j.cma.2005.04.010
- 5) Balasubramaniam, K., & Sridhar, C.V. (1991), "Spectral element formulation for dynamic analysis of a coupled piezoelectric wafer and beam system", *Journal of Sound and Vibration*, Vol. 150 No. 1, pp. 117-127. doi:10.1016/j.compstruc.2010.01.010
- 6) Chakraborty, A., & Gopalakrishnan, S. (2006), "A novel formulation of a spectral plate element for wave propagation in isotropic structures", *Acta Mechanica*, Vol. 187 No. 1-4, pp. 13-38. doi:10.1016/j.fincl.2009.05.002
- 7) Castaings, M., Le Clezio, E., & Hosten, B. (2002), "Study of the fundamental Lamb modes interaction with asymmetrical discontinuities", *Ultrasonics*, Vol. 40 No. 1-8, pp. 709-714. doi:10.1016/j.ndteint.2008.01.004
- 8) Lowe, M.J.S., Challis, R.E., & Chan, C.W. (2000), "Leaky Lamb waves for the detection and sizing of defects in bonded aluminium lap joints", *Review of Progress in Quantitative Nondestructive Evaluation*, Vol. 19, pp. 1261-1268. doi:10.1016/j.ndteint.2005.02.004
- 9) Lowe, M.J.S., & Diligent, O. (2002), "Study of the fundamental Lamb modes interaction with symmetrical notches", *Review of Progress in Quantitative Nondestructive Evaluation*, Vol. 21, pp. 89-96. doi:10.1016/j.ndteint.2007.07.001
- 10) Mustapha, S., Ye, L., Wang, D., & Lu, Y. (2011), "Assessment of debonding in sandwich CF/EP composite beams using A0 Lamb wave at low frequency", *Composite Structures*, Vol. 93 No. 2, pp. 483-491. doi:10.1016/j.compstruct.2010.08.032
- 11) Castaings, M., Le Clezio, E., & Hosten, B. (2002), "Simple expressions of the reflection and transmission coefficients of fundamental lamb waves by a rectangular notch", *Journal of the Acoustical Society of America*, Vol. 111 No. 1, pp. 64-74. doi:10.1016/j.ultras.2011.03.001
- 12) Baronian, V., Lhémy, A., & Bonnet-BenDhia, A.S. (2010), "The use of an orthogonality relation for reducing the size of finite element models for 3D guided waves scattering problems", *Mathematical and Computer Modelling*, Vol. 52 No. 9-10, pp. 1299-1309. doi:10.1016/j.ultras.2008.01.005

- 13) Mažeika, L., Kažys, R., Raišutis, R., & Demčenko, A. (2009), "Lamb wave mode decomposition using concentric ring and circular piezoelectric transducers", *Ultrasonics*, Vol. 49 No. 2, pp. 225-233. doi:10.1016/j.wavemoti.2011.01.001
- 14) Castaings, M., & Hosten, B. (2001), "Semi-analytical formulation for the guided waves-based reconstruction of elastic moduli", *Ultrasonics*, Vol. 39 No. 3, pp. 195-201. doi:10.1016/j.ymsp.2011.02.004
- 15) Kausel, E. (2006), "Semi-analytical evaluation of integral forms associated with Lamb's problem", *Journal of Engineering Mechanics*, Vol. 132 No. 5, pp. 578-580. doi:10.1016/j.soildyn.2008.04.007
- 16) Lowe, M.J.S., Challis, R.E., & Chan, C.W. (2000), "Propagation of guided waves in bonded composite structures with tapered adhesive layer", *Journal of the Acoustical Society of America*, Vol. 108 No. 1, pp. 123-132. doi:10.1016/j.apm.2011.04.042
- 17) Treysède, F. (2008), "A semi-analytical finite element formulation for modeling stress wave propagation in axisymmetric damped waveguides", *Journal of Sound and Vibration*, Vol. 314 No. 3-5, pp. 707-727. doi:10.1016/j.jsv.2008.04.028
- 18) Bai, H., Shah, A.H., Popplewell, N., & Datta, S.K. (2004), "Numerical modeling of guided wave interaction with non-axisymmetric cracks in elastic cylinders", *Journal of Applied Mechanics*, Vol. 71 No. 6, pp. 798-809. doi:10.1016/j.ijsolstr.2010.11.013